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TAX INCENTIVES AND PERFORMANCE OF CONSUMER GOODS COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

Unachukwu, I. Chukwukamnene Ph. D and Chukwujama, Ngozi Comfort

Department of Business Administration,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University

E-mail: taureanpharma@gmail.com,
ngo4real1190@yahoo.com

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Abstract: This study investigated the effect of tax incentives on the performance of Nigerian consumer goods companies from 2010 to 2024. Specifically, this study aimed to determine the extent to which tax relief, capital allowance, investment allowance, and balancing allowance affect the return on assets of consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Four research questions were developed, and the four hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The relevant conceptual, theoretical, and empirical literature was reviewed. This study was anchored on the normative theory of tax incentives. An ex-post-facto research design was adopted. The study population comprises of the entire 21 consumer goods companies on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group. Six consumer goods companies were purposively selected for this study. Secondary data were sourced from the annual reports of the sampled consumer goods companies. Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression analysis were used to analyze the data. The study found that tax relief, capital allowance, and investment allowance have a significant effect on consumer goods companies' return on assets in Nigeria. The study also found that balancing allowance had no significant effect on consumer goods companies' return on assets in Nigeria. Based on the foregoing, the study concludes that tax incentives have a significant positive effect on the performance of CG companies in Nigeria. The study recommends, among others, that since tax relief has a significant positive effect on performance, the government should streamline and expand tax relief programs targeted at the consumer goods sector through the FIRS. This includes simplifying eligibility requirements and automating processes to ensure timely and consistent relief application.

Keywords: Tax incentives, tax relief, capital allowance, investment allowance, balancing Allowance and Return on Assets.

INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing is a key driver of Nigeria's structural transformation, employment generation, and export diversification. Despite abundant natural resources and a large domestic market, the Nigerian manufacturing

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sector, particularly those involved in the production of consumer goods, has faced recurring challenges ranging from inconsistent policy environment, poor infrastructure (power, transport), high cost of finance, and competition from imported goods. To stimulate industrial growth, attract investment, and improve competitiveness, successive Nigerian governments have implemented fiscal measures, including tax incentives (tax holidays, tax credits, reduced tax rates, accelerated depreciation, investment allowances, import duty waivers, and tax exemptions for pioneer industries). Taxation is a major source of revenue for governments; however, excessive or poorly structured tax regimes can stifle business growth, reduce investment, and limit profitability (Nwidobie, 2020). In response, governments around the world, including Nigeria, often introduce **tax incentives** such as tax holidays, capital allowances, investment tax credits, and exemptions as mechanisms to reduce tax burdens, stimulate investment, and improve enterprise performance (Sebele-Mpofu, Gomera, & Sibanda, 2022). Such incentives are particularly important in the banking sector due to the high compliance costs and regulatory pressures that banks face.

Currently, almost all developing countries and many developed ones provide various forms of inducements to companies, such as reductions or exemptions from import duties and income taxes for specified periods (Bird, 2020). These incentives are introduced for different purposes. In some instances, they are designed to counterbalance investment disincentives embedded within the general tax system. In other cases, they aim to mitigate broader challenges faced by investors, including inadequate infrastructure, outdated and complex legal frameworks, bureaucratic inefficiencies, and weak administrative systems, whether in taxation or other sectors (Philips, 2020).

Two key premises form the foundation for advocating tax incentive programs in developing countries. Increased investment is essential to accelerate economic growth, and tax breaks can effectively stimulate such investment (Jun, 2022). Although these assumptions may appear straightforward, they require careful qualification to fully understand the effectiveness and broader implications of investment tax incentives (Cui, Hicks & Xing, 2022). Two prevailing perspectives exist on the usefulness of fiscal incentives. Proponents contend that these incentives encourage investment, create employment opportunities, and promote overall economic development. Conversely, critics argue that tax incentives often lead to inequities, impose high fiscal costs when investments would have occurred regardless, and open avenues for tax avoidance schemes that ultimately erode the revenue base (Kronfol & Steenbergen, 2020).

The Nigerian government has implemented several reforms, such as the Finance Acts of 2019, 2020, and 2023, to enhance the ease of doing business and strengthen the country's productive sectors. These reforms introduced various incentives, including reductions in minimum tax rates and tax exemptions for small and medium enterprises and manufacturing companies. Such measures are intended to improve operational efficiency, boost liquidity, and ultimately enhance firm performance (Ezeagu et al., 2024). However, despite these initiatives, the impact of tax incentives on Nigeria's consumer goods firms' performance remains unsatisfactory. While some empirical studies indicate that tax incentives positively influence profitability, asset utilization, and shareholder value (Chukwumerije & Akinyomi, 2021), others highlight issues that undermine their effectiveness, such as policy inconsistency, lack of transparency, and poor implementation (Habila, Jim-Suleiman, & Uchendu, 2024).

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Moreover, these incentives often disproportionately favor larger firms, leaving smaller enterprises disadvantaged and raising questions about equity and long-term sustainability.

Empirical evidence from many countries shows mixed outcomes: some studies find that tax incentives increase investment and improve firm-level performance, while others report little or no effect once other constraints (infrastructure, regulatory bottlenecks, firm capabilities) are accounted for. In Nigeria, the effectiveness of manufacturing tax incentives has been questioned because incentive packages are sometimes opaque, temporary, unevenly applied, and not always accompanied by complementary reforms (e.g., stable power supply, access to finance, and skills development). Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the effect of tax incentives on the performance of CG companies in Nigeria.

Statement of the problem

Nigeria's consumer goods sector remains one of the key drivers of sustainable economic growth, employment generation, and industrial development. Despite its strategic importance, the sector continues to perform below expectations, contributing less than its potential to national output and export earnings. Persistent challenges, such as inadequate infrastructure, high production costs, policy instability, and limited access to credit, have hindered the competitiveness of manufacturing. In response, successive Nigerian governments have introduced various tax incentives, such as pioneer status incentives, investment tax credits, capital allowances, and import duty exemptions, to stimulate industrial growth, attract foreign direct investment, and enhance firm performance. Despite government efforts to create an enabling environment through tax incentives, the effectiveness of these policies remains largely unknown. Nigerian policymakers and regulators have been unable to ascertain whether these fiscal interventions are achieving their intended results in the consumer goods sector. As a result, empirical research that addresses this gap by examining how tax incentives have affected key financial metrics of Nigeria's consumer goods sector is critical.

Despite the existence of various tax incentive schemes in Nigeria, empirical evidence regarding their actual impact on firm performance remains limited. Empirical studies have yielded mixed and sometimes contradictory findings. For instance, Otumba (2015) reported that tax incentive measures were instrumental in stimulating the performance of SMEs. Similarly, Chukwumerije and Akinyomi (2021) found that tax incentives significantly influence firms' profitability, staff strength, and overall growth and development. Similarly, Mauda and Saidu (2019) revealed that capital allowance and loss relief exerted a positive and significant effect on firm performance, while Olowo, Anisere-Hammed, and Adewole (2020) established that corporate income tax incentives positively and significantly affect return on assets. Conversely, other studies reported divergent outcomes. Ondabu, Muturi, and Kisaka (2016) found that tax incentives exert an insignificant effect on firm performance, while Mauda and Saidu (2019) observed that investment allowance, though positive, had an insignificant impact on financial performance. Similarly, Onyango (2015) identified a negative relationship between investment deductions, industrial building deductions, and financial performance. Overall, the empirical literature reveals inconsistent findings across different sectors, with limited attention given to Nigeria's consumer goods industry. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no study has specifically examined the effect of tax incentives on the performance of Nigerian consumer goods companies. Therefore,

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this study seeks to fill this gap by investigating whether tax incentives effectively enhance the performance of consumer goods firms in the Nigerian context.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of tax incentives on the performance of Nigeria's consumer goods companies. The specific objectives include the following:

1. Determine the effect of tax relief on consumer goods companies' return on assets in Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the effect of capital allowance on the return on assets of Nigerian consumer goods companies.
3. Determine the effect of investment allowance on consumer goods companies' return on assets in Nigeria.
4. Examine the effect of balancing allowance on the return on assets of Nigerian consumer goods companies.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. To what extent does tax relief affect consumer goods companies' return on assets in Nigeria?
2. To what extent does capital allowance affect consumer goods companies' return on assets in Nigeria?
3. To what extent does investment allowance affect the return on assets of Nigerian consumer goods companies?
4. To what extent balance allowance affect consumer goods companies' return on assets in Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were developed to guide this study:

Ho₁: Tax relief has no significant effect on consumer goods companies' return on assets in Nigeria.

Ho₂: Capital allowance has no significant effect on consumer goods companies' return on assets in Nigeria.

Ho₃: Investment allowance has no significant effect on consumer goods companies' return on assets in Nigeria.

Ho₄: Balancing allowance has no significant effect on the return on assets of Nigerian consumer goods companies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Tax Incentives

Tax incentives are defined as tax provisions that deviate from the general principles of tax neutrality and fairness and are designed to encourage both foreign and domestic investment. These incentives aim to enhance the competitiveness of investment among developing nations, maximize returns on investment, and minimize inefficiencies and costs in the investment environment (Okoth, 2023). According to Azeez, Olabanji, and Emmanuel (2018), tax incentives encompass all government measures intended to motivate taxpayers to comply with tax obligations. Such measures often involve policy adjustments that lessen the tax burden on specific industries, groups, or services. They may include the adoption of lower tax rates, dissemination of fiscal information by tax authorities, or even total exemption from taxation (Abdulrahman & Kabir, 2017).

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Similarly, Nwidobie (2020) defines tax incentives as deliberate reductions in tax liabilities granted by the government to encourage particular economic units, such as corporate bodies, to act in desired ways for example, to invest more, employing more people, exporting more, or conserving resources. These reductions can be achieved by lowering tax rates, reducing the tax base, or providing exemptions. Mauda and Saidu (2019) further explain that tax incentives may take the form of tax holidays or tax burden reductions for investors engaged in specific sectors, such as manufacturing, mining, oil and gas, exports, and agriculture, that promote national development or alleviate the economic burden on citizens. The Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS, 2018) identifies various tax incentives, including personal allowance, capital allowance, investment allowance, loss relief, rollover relief, annual allowance, pioneer relief, tax-free dividends, export processing zone relief, research and development relief, and tax-free holidays.

According to Tapang, Onodi, and Amaraihu (2018), tax incentives include special exclusions, exemptions, deductions, or credits that provide preferential tax treatment, such as tax holidays, investment allowances, tax credits, accelerated depreciation, and reduced tax rates. These fiscal measures are intended to attract both domestic and foreign capital to specific economic activities or geographic areas. Olowo, Anisere-Hammed, and Adewole (2020) observed that governments globally use tax incentives to stimulate private investment in priority sectors such as tourism. Such incentives are often designed to offset differences in business costs across regions that may stem from variations in taxation, labor, transportation, or other operational expenses (Peters & Kiabel, 2015). Tax incentives make investments more attractive and ultimately enhance firm profitability by raising the return on capital (Mauda & Saidu, 2019). Finally, Okauru (2019) describes tax incentives as exemptions or reliefs granted to individuals or companies to mitigate the impact of taxation, thereby encouraging savings and investment. However, distinguishing between provisions that form part of the general tax system and those that provide special treatment can be challenging—a distinction that becomes increasingly significant as nations face constraints in implementing targeted tax incentives.

Tax Relief

Tax relief refers to any program, deduction, credit, or incentive designed to reduce individuals' or businesses' tax liability. The form and extent of such relief typically depend on factors such as a country's tax laws, income levels, and specific circumstances such as disability, natural disasters, or dependents (Mauda & Saidu, 2019). According to Olowo et al. (2020), tax relief encompasses mechanisms that lower an individual's or entity's tax burden. These mechanisms may include deductions (e.g., medical expenses or mortgage interest), tax credits (e.g., those granted for childcare or education), and exemptions.

In certain cases, governments introduce tax relief measures as temporary responses to economic downturns or natural disasters to reduce financial pressure on affected individuals and businesses. Such relief can take various forms, including tax credits for families with children or individuals with disabilities, deductions for charitable donations or business expenses, and tax deferrals or rate reductions. Therefore, tax relief may be either permanent or temporary, depending on the prevailing economic conditions and policy objectives (IRS, 2006).

Capital Allowances

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Capital allowances refer to tax reliefs granted to businesses on their capital expenditures (Okoth, 2023). They represent deductions permitted by tax authorities that enable firms to reduce their taxable income by writing off the cost of acquiring qualifying fixed assets such as machinery, equipment, vehicles, or buildings over a specified period. According to Jun (2022), capital allowance denotes the portion of capital investment costs, or funds committed to a company's long-term growth, that a business can deduct annually from its revenue through depreciation. These allowances are sometimes referred to as depreciation allowances.

Capital allowances are designed to help businesses recover the costs of their capital investments. These allowances effectively reduce taxable income and provide financial relief by allowing firms to claim depreciation or amortization on qualifying assets. This system serves as an incentive for businesses to invest in long-term productive assets, promoting economic growth. The deduction process typically involves allocating the cost of an asset over its useful life, subject to specific rules and regulations that vary across asset types and tax jurisdictions (Olowo, Anisere-Hammed & Adewole, 2020).

Investment Allowance

Investment allowance is a form of tax incentive that grants businesses a deduction or tax relief on capital investments such as the acquisition of machinery, plants, or equipment (Tirimba, Muturi, & Sifunjo, 2016). It is specifically designed to stimulate investment in new assets by providing a reduction in taxable income based on the amount spent on qualifying investments. Essentially, investment allowances reduce a company's immediate tax burden by enabling it to write off the cost of eligible assets more rapidly than under standard depreciation methods (Mataba, Lassourd, Readhead & Nikièma, 2023). This form of allowance is typically available to businesses that invest in fixed capital assets used for productive purposes, subject to certain conditions or limitations depending on the tax jurisdiction. Companies engaged in agricultural production (excluding marketing and processing) are granted an investment allowance of 10% as an incentive for increased investment. This allowance is provided in addition to the initial allowance on such assets and, like the initial allowance, is granted once per asset, irrespective of the length of the basis period during which the asset was first put to use (Zee, Stotsky & Ley, 2022).

Balancing Allowance and Balancing Charge

Balancing allowance and charge are important concepts in taxation, particularly in relation to capital asset treatment. Both terms concern capital allowance adjustment when an asset is sold, disposed of, or ceases to be in use. A balancing allowance arises when an asset is sold or disposed of for an amount less than its tax written down value (TWDV) that is, the residual value of the asset after accounting for previous capital allowances or depreciation (Amendola, Boccia, Mele & Sensini, 2018). In such cases, the remaining unclaimed value is allowed as an additional tax deduction in the disposal year. A balancing charge represents the opposite situation (Abdul, Aruwa, & Adamu, 2018). It occurs when an asset is sold or disposed of for more than its tax value. In this case, the business must repay the excess capital allowances previously claimed on the asset. Therefore, the balancing charge is added back to the taxable income, effectively increasing the firm's tax liability for that period.

Performance

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Performance refers to a set of financial and non-financial indicators that provide information on the extent to which organizational objectives and desired outcomes have been achieved (Lebans & Euske, 2016). It is a dynamic concept that requires judgment and interpretation, which is often reflected through financial reporting. The understanding of firm performance may vary depending on the evaluator's perspective; for instance, an internal stakeholder may assess performance differently from an external observer. Firm performance is one of the key outputs of an accounting system, designed to provide users with essential information to make informed economic decisions regarding an enterprise's profitability and operational efficiency. Therefore, defining firm performance involves identifying its key elements and characteristics as they relate to various areas of organizational responsibility.

The common financial ratios used to assess organizational performance typically fall into two categories: profitability and growth. These include return on assets, return on investment, return on equity, return on sales, revenue growth, market share, stock price, sales growth, liquidity, and operational efficiency (Mainelli & Giffords, 2020). In this study, ROA is employed as the primary measure of firm performance. ROA assesses the overall efficiency with which a firm uses its assets to generate net income from operations. It reflects management's effectiveness in deploying capital and indicates how well resources are being used to produce profits. ROA is calculated by dividing profit after tax (PAT) and interest by total assets, representing the ratio of net income to total assets. It is widely regarded as one of the most comprehensive measures of operating performance because it is relatively straightforward to interpret and links operational results with the resources employed to achieve them.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the NT of tax incentives. The theory does not originate from a single scholar but has evolved over time through contributions from various fields, such as public finance, welfare economics, and optimal taxation theory. It draws particularly from the works of Arthur Cecil Pigou on externalities, James Mirrlees on optimal tax theory, Richard Musgrave on public finance, and Joseph Stiglitz on imperfect markets and tax design. Collectively, these scholars provided the normative foundation for evaluating and designing tax incentives that align with broader social welfare objectives. The normative theory of tax incentives emphasizes the design and implementation of tax incentives to achieve socially desirable outcomes. Rooted in normative economics, the theory is concerned with value judgments about what is "good," "fair," or "optimal" for society. Unlike positive theories, which describe how things are, the normative theory is prescriptive and guides policymakers on how tax incentives should function to promote efficiency, fairness, and welfare.

According to this theory, the effectiveness of tax incentives largely depends on contextual factors such as the structure of the economy, the competence of the tax administration, the nature of the targeted investment, and the government's fiscal capacity. Thus, no universal model of tax incentives fits all economies. The ideal incentive is one that stimulates investment in the desired sector or region, minimizes revenue leakage, and limits tax avoidance or manipulation opportunities. However, tax incentive allocation also presents governance challenges. Because incentives confer financial benefits, they are susceptible to abuse and corruption if they are not transparently administered. Consequently, proponents of the normative approach argue that all investors

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who meet predetermined, open, and transparent criteria should automatically receive tax incentives. Conversely, another school of thought suggests that incentives should be tailored to each investment, providing just enough inducement to encourage participation without excessive fiscal cost. The choice between these approaches often depends on a country's strength of governance and institutional transparency.

Under the normative framework, moderate and well-targeted tax incentives, particularly those aimed at new investments in machinery, equipment, and research and development, are considered most effective. Such incentives provide upfront support, create positive signaling effects, and stimulate productive investment without causing significant revenue losses (Chukwumerije & Akinyomi, 2021). Policy instruments, such as investment tax credits and capital allowances, are examples of targeted mechanisms that align with this principle. Furthermore, maintaining corporate tax rates at levels comparable to those of neighboring or competing economies is a sound approach. However, excessively reducing rates below 20%–30%, as observed in capital-exporting countries, can result in greater revenue losses than the investment gains achieved (Fletcher, 2013).

Empirical Review

The issue of tax incentives has received considerable attention in the academic literature, with numerous studies examining their impact on firm performance, investment, and economic growth across different contexts. Okoth (2023) investigated the effects of tax incentives and subsidies on economic growth in developing countries, focusing on Indonesia, Kenya, Malaysia, and Türkiye. Using secondary data obtained from the World Bank, IMF, and OECD covering the period 2010–2022, panel data regression analysis was employed to assess the relationship between tax incentives and economic development. The results revealed that subsidies exerted a positive and significant effect on investment and economic growth, whereas tax incentives on production, sales, transfers, and capital gains had an insignificant positive effect on investment but a negative, though insignificant, effect on economic growth.

Similarly, Chukwumerije and Akinyomi (2021) examined the impact of tax incentives on the performance of small-scale industries in Rivers State, Nigeria. Eleven out of 22 registered small-scale food and beverage manufacturing industries were randomly selected, and data were collected through questionnaires administered to 260 respondents. Using frequency distribution and chi-square analysis, the study found that operators were well aware of the various tax incentives available to them. The results further revealed that tax incentives significantly and positively influenced small-scale industries' profitability, staff strength, and overall growth and development.

In another Nigerian study, Olowo, Anisere-Hammed, and Adewole (2020) assessed the effect of tax incentives on manufacturing firms' growth and development. Adopting an ex-post facto research design, the study used secondary data on corporate income tax incentives, capital allowance incentives, customs duty incentives, excise tax incentives, and return on assets (ROA) from 2013 to 2018. Using multiple regression analysis via E-view 9.0, the findings indicated that all forms of tax incentives, including corporate income tax, capital allowance, customs duty, and excise tax incentives, had positive and significant effects on ROA. The study

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concluded that tax incentives play a vital role in promoting manufacturing firms' growth and development in Nigeria.

Mauda and Saidu (2019) examined the impact of tax incentives on firm performance among Nigerian listed consumer goods companies from 2000 to 2017. The study used data from annual reports, the Investment Promotion Commission, and the FIRS. Of the 21 listed companies, seven were selected based on data availability. Using Pearson's correlation and multiple regression analyses, the study found that capital allowance and loss relief had positive and significant effects on firm performance, whereas investment allowance exhibited a positive but insignificant effect.

Olabisi (2019) investigated the catalytic effect of tax incentives on economic development in Nigeria using a sample of 12 purposively selected companies in Lagos, Nigeria. Employing chi-square analysis for hypothesis testing, the study found that extending tax incentives to all deserving companies would significantly enhance Nigeria's economic growth.

Amendola et al. (2018) explored the influence of tax incentives on corporate profitability in the Dominican Republic using firm-level data from 2006 to 2015. Employing panel data analytical techniques, the study found that corporate income tax exemptions positively affected profitability. However, irregular tax assessments across corporate entities distorted competition in several sectors, particularly in manufacturing, thereby negatively impacting overall economic efficiency.

Abdul, Aruwa, and Adamu (2018) investigated the relationship between tax incentives and entrepreneurship in Nigeria. Using an exploratory survey approach and reviewing secondary data from government publications, journals, and related studies, the authors found that tax incentives positively and significantly influence entrepreneurship outcomes such as wealth creation, employment generation, and community development. The study recommends the implementation of well-structured incentives that adhere to sound taxation principles.

Tembur (2016) analyzed the effect of tax incentives on the financial performance of export processing zone (EPZ) firms in Kenya. The study employed a quantitative descriptive design, drawing a sample of 70 firms registered with the Export Processing Zone Authority as of 2016. Secondary data obtained from the Kenya Revenue Authority and EPZA were analyzed using multiple regression. The findings revealed a weak but positive relationship between tax incentives and financial performance. Additionally, while asset utilization efficiency was significantly related to firm performance, firm size exhibited a negative relationship with financial performance.

Similarly, Ondabu, Muturi, and Kisaka (2016) examined the effects of tax incentives on the performance of listed firms in Kenya, focusing on the stock market performance. The study adopted a descriptive design and involved 30 firms listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange (NSE). Both primary and secondary data were collected from 150 respondents using stratified random sampling. Data were analyzed using Stata (version 13), using correlation, multiple regression, analysis of variance, and t-tests. The results indicated that tax incentives had an insignificant effect on NSE performance, indicating a limited influence on stock market outcomes.

Uwuigbe, Uwuigbe, Adeyemo, and Anowai (2016) conducted a study on tax incentives and manufacturing firms' growth in Nigeria. The study employed regression analysis for hypothesis testing using structured

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questionnaires distributed to 100 employees in selected manufacturing firms. The findings showed that tax incentives significantly influenced the availability of funds for investment, enhanced tax compliance, and contributed to the expansion of manufacturing industries in Nigeria. The study further recommended increased firm awareness regarding available tax incentives.

Tirimba, Muturi, and Sifunjo (2016) analyzed the relationship between tax incentives and firm profitability among companies listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange. Data were collected from both primary and secondary sources and analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation, and multiple regression analyses. The study found that tax incentives had an insignificant effect on corporate performance, implying that tax incentives alone may not play a decisive role in improving firm profitability.

Finally, Onyango (2015) investigated the effect of tax incentives on the financial performance of five-star hotels in Nairobi County, Kenya. The study adopted a quantitative descriptive design and conducted a census of all seven five-star hotels in the county. Using data provided by management accountants and analyzed through multiple regression, the study found that tax incentives accounted for 89.5% of the variation in financial performance. Specifically, wear-and-tear deductions had a strong positive relationship with firm performance, whereas investment and industrial building deductions had a negative association with firm performance. The study recommended that the government continue to support wear-and-tear incentives while reviewing investment and building deduction policies to improve their effectiveness.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted an ex-post facto research design, which relies on existing data that are suitable for analytical investigation but were not originally collected for research purposes. The study employed secondary data obtained from the annual reports and financial statements of selected consumer goods companies in Nigeria. These data covered a five-year period (2010–2024). The variables used in the study include ROA as a proxy for firm performance, while tax relief, capital allowance, investment allowance, and balancing allowance served as the independent variables representing tax incentives.

The study population comprised 21 consumer goods companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of December 2024. Using a purposive sampling technique, six (6) companies were selected for detailed analysis based on data availability and relevance. These companies are: Vitafoam Nigeria Plc, Unilever Nigeria Plc, PZ Cussons Nigeria Plc, Nigerian Breweries Plc, Nestlé Nigeria Plc, and Guinness Nigeria Plc.

The collected data were analyzed using several econometric and statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics were first employed to examine the variables' individual characteristics. Unit root and cointegration tests were conducted to determine the stationarity and long-run relationship among the variables. Correlation analysis was conducted to identify the degree of association and test for possible multicollinearity among the variables.

The study used the OLS estimation technique for hypothesis testing and model evaluation, implemented through the E-Views econometric software. The OLS method was selected due to its desirable properties of unbiasedness, consistency, efficiency, linearity, and computational simplicity, making it a suitable and reliable tool for the estimation of relationships.

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One model was developed to capture the effect of tax incentives on the performance of Nigerian consumer goods companies. The linear regression model is expressed in a functional form as follows:

$$ROA = f(TR, CA, IA, \text{ and } BA) \tag{1}$$

Where

- ROA = Return on Assets
- TR = Tax Relief
- CA = Capital Allowance
- IA = Investment Allowance
- BA = Balancing Allowance

This equation can be restated in an econometric form as follows:

$$ROA = a_0 + a_1TR + a_2CA + a_3IA + a_4BA + \mu \tag{2}$$

Where

- a_0 = autonomous or intercept
- a_1 to a_4 = coefficient of parameter tax incentives
- μ = Stochastic variable or error term

RESULTS

The data obtained from the annual reports and statement of accounts of the respective consumer goods companies in Nigeria were subjected to statistical estimation and analysis to determine the effect of tax incentives on performance.

Descriptive Statistics

This section presents the descriptive statistics on the effect of tax incentives on the performance of Nigeria’s consumer goods companies. This analysis aims to examine the behavior and distribution of the variables over the study period. The individual characteristics of these variables are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Descriptive statistics of the study

	ROA	TR	CA	IA	BA
Mean	0.132788	108053.1	13134.52	5187.800	2756.800
Median	0.078000	72542.00	405.0000	2489.000	681.0000
Maximum	0.778000	406992.0	78074.00	18648.00	7616.000
Minimum	0.001000	3973.000	108.0000	165.0000	356.0000
Std. Dev.	0.166964	103868.6	23906.85	5837.354	2833.232
Skewness	2.467154	1.342420	1.820587	1.290438	0.606183
Kurtosis	9.953294	4.165351	4.828068	3.111696	1.613795
Jarque-Bera	75.72468	8.923340	17.29165	6.951451	3.532703
Probability	0.128651	0.111543	0.452176	0.330939	0.243956
Sum	3.319700	2701327.	328363.0	129695.0	68920.00
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.669046	2.59E+11	1.37E+10	8.18E+08	1.93E+08

Source: E-View version 8.0

This table presents the summary statistics of the variables used in this study. Key information, including the mean, median, maximum, and minimum values, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis, and Jarque-Bera statistics, is provided for each variable. The mean return on assets (ROA), which serves as a proxy for firm

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performance, was 0.132788, while the mean values for tax relief (TR), capital allowance (CA), investment allowance (IA), and balancing allowance (BA) were 108,053.1, 13,134.52, 5,187.8, and 2,756.8, respectively. The median, a robust measure of central tendency that is less sensitive to outliers, was 0.078 for ROA, 72,542.0 for TR, 405.0 for CA, 2,489.0 for IA, and 681.0 for BA. Some variables exhibited standard deviations greater than their respective means, indicating a wide variation in these variables across the sampled companies.

Skewness, which measures the asymmetry of the distribution around the mean, was positive for all variables, indicating that the data are right-skewed; that is, the right tail of the distribution is longer than the left tail. The kurtosis values for ROA, TR, CA, IA, and BA were 52.467154, 1.342420, 1.820587, 1.290438, and 0.606183, respectively. The Jarque-Bera statistic tests for normality was performed by examining differences in skewness and kurtosis. The ROA, TR, CA, IA, and BA values were 75.72468, 8.923334, 17.29165, 6.951451, and 3.532703, respectively. All variables exhibited Jarque-Bera probabilities of >0.05 , indicating that they are normally distributed and suitable for further analysis. Finally, 90 observations were made for each variable was 90.

Correlation Analysis

A common method for detecting multicollinearity in a model is the use of a correlation matrix. This involves examining the degree of correlation among the independent variables, and the results are presented in a matrix format. Since multicollinearity is a matter of degree rather than absolute existence, a correlation coefficient above 0.8 indicates a high degree of multicollinearity in the model. The correlation matrix for the variables used in this study is presented in Table 1.

Table 2 Correlation matrix

	ROA	TA	CA	IA	BA
ROA	1.000000				
TA	0.025716	1.000000			
CA	0.146489	0.643345	1.000000		
IA	0.233390	0.060689	0.065366	1.000000	
BA	0.381998	0.205363	0.490106	0.021477	1.000000

Source: E-View version 8.0

The correlation matrix indicates that the degree of correlation among the independent variables is low or moderate, indicating the absence of multicollinearity. According to Wan, Shahnaz, and Nurasyikin (2008), the Pearson correlation coefficient (R) between any pair of independent variables should not exceed 0.80; values above this threshold may indicate potential multicollinearity. The highest observed correlation is 0.643345 between capital allowance and balancing allowance is 0.643345, which falls below the critical threshold. This confirms that multicollinearity is not a concern among the variables used in the model.

Regression Result

The regression result is presented in Table 3. To analyze this table, we shall employ two criteria: statistical and econometric.

Table 3 Estimation results

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Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.808888	14.14473	2.127884	0.0006
TR	0.266233	0.378621	2.703165	0.0005
IA	0.677447	0.373995	2.811379	0.0059
BA	1.617669	0.749805	0.157453	0.1440
CA	0.564862	0.420305	2.343933	0.0348

R-squared	0.639327	Mean var dependent	-2.866197
Adjusted R-squared	0.565466	S.D.-dependent var	1.636468
F-statistic	32.51714	Durbin-Watson stat	1.963805
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000733		

Source: Authors' computation from E-View version 8.0

The regression analysis indicates that tax relief has a positive and significant effect on ROA, implying that a unit increase in tax relief results in a 0.266233 increase in ROA. Similarly, capital allowance exhibits a positive and significant relationship with ROA, indicating that a unit increase in capital allowance leads to a 6.564862 increase in ROA, holding other factors constant. Investment allowance also has a positive and significant effect on ROA, whereas balancing allowance has a positive but insignificant effect on ROA.

Several diagnostic measures were employed to assess the statistical relevance of these results, including the t-statistic, F-statistic, t-probability, R^2 , and adjusted R^2 .

T-statistic: The t-statistic evaluates the individual significance of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The t-statistic is expressed as follows: Typically, a t-value of 2 indicates significance. In this study, all independent variables, except balancing allowance, were found to have a significant effect on firm performance.

F-statistic: The F-statistic measures the joint significance of all independent variables. Its significance is determined using F-probability. If the F-probability is less than 0.05, the independent variables are considered jointly significant. In this study, the F-probability is 0.000733, indicating that the independent variables collectively have a significant impact on performance.

Coefficient of Determination (R^2): R^2 measures the model's overall goodness of fit, indicating the proportion of variation in the dependent variable explained by the independent variables. In this study, R^2 is 63.9%, meaning that variations in tax incentives jointly explain about 63.9% of the variation in ROA.

Adjusted R^2 : Adjusted R^2 accounts for the model's degrees of freedom. In this analysis, the adjusted R^2 is 56.5%, suggesting that the independent variables explain 56.5% of the variation in firm performance after adjusting for sample size and the number of predictors.

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T-probability (t-prob): The t-probability complements the t-statistic. Values less than 0.05 indicate significance at the 5% level. Consistent with the t-statistics, all variables except balancing allowance are statistically significant.

Serial Correlation Test: One assumption of the CLRM is that error terms are not serially correlated. The presence of autocorrelation was tested using the Durbin-Watson (D) statistic. A value approximating 2 indicates no autocorrelation. In this study, the D-statistic is 1.963805, confirming the absence of autocorrelation and validating the model for reliable forecasting.

Hypothesis Testing

The hypotheses expressed in Chapter One are tested using the t-statistics and t-probabilities presented in Table 3, as these measures evaluate the individual significance of the independent variables in explaining firm performance. The results confirm that tax relief, capital allowance, and investment allowance significantly influence consumer goods companies' performance, whereas balancing allowance does not have a statistically significant effect.

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Tax relief has no significant effect on consumer goods companies' return on assets in Nigeria.

To test this hypothesis, we employed the t-statistic coefficient from the regression results. The t-value for tax relief is 2.703165, with a corresponding probability of 0.0005, indicating high statistical significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and it is concluded that tax relief has a significant effect on consumer goods companies' return on assets in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Capital allowance has no significant effect on consumer goods companies' return on assets in Nigeria.

The t-statistic for capital allowance is 2.343933 from the regression results, with a corresponding probability of 0.0012, indicating high statistical significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and it is concluded that capital allowance has a significant effect on the return on assets of consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three

Ho₃: Investment allowance has no significant effect on consumer goods companies' return on assets in Nigeria.

The regression results show that the t-statistic for investment allowance is 2.811379, with a corresponding probability of 0.0059, indicating high statistical significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and it is concluded that investment allowance has a significant effect on the return on assets of consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Four

Ho₄: Balancing allowance has no significant effect on the return on assets of Nigerian consumer goods companies.

From the regression results, the t-statistic for balancing allowance is 0.157453, with a corresponding probability of 0.1440, indicating that it is statistically insignificant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, and it is concluded that balancing allowance has no significant effect on the return on assets of consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

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DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

This study investigated the influence of various tax incentives, namely, tax relief, capital allowance, investment allowance, and balancing allowance, on consumer goods companies' return on assets (ROA) in Nigeria. The findings have important implications for tax policy and corporate financial performance. The analysis revealed that tax relief has a significant positive effect on ROA. This finding aligns with previous studies suggesting that tax incentives enhance business performance by reducing the effective tax burden (Chukwumerije & Akinyomi, 2021). By receiving tax relief, consumer goods companies retain more earnings, which can be reinvested into operations, expansion, or innovation, thereby improving profitability and asset use. This result is consistent with the neo-classical investment theory, which posits that lowering taxes reduces capital costs and encourages investment (Anyanwu, 2010). The findings highlight that targeted tax reliefs can effectively stimulate improved financial performance within the consumer goods sector.

Similarly, capital allowance had a significant effect on ROA. This supports Okoth's (2023) argument that capital allowances incentivize reinvestment by permitting deductions on qualifying capital expenditures. Capital allowances reduce overall cost structures by lowering taxable income, leading to improved profitability measures such as ROA. These results corroborate empirical research linking tax-related capital investment incentives with firm-level performance improvements (Mauda & Saidu, 2019).

The study further found that the investment allowance significantly influences the ROA. The investment allowance provides additional deductions on qualifying investments, thereby reducing taxable income. The positive association suggests that consumer goods companies are responsive to such incentives, and investment allowances act as a catalyst for enhancing asset performance. This finding supports Tembur (2016), who noted that targeted investment incentives stimulate capital formation and create a competitive advantage for firms that effectively utilize them. For consumer goods companies, this may translate into the acquisition of advanced technologies or expansion of operations, ultimately boosting returns.

Interestingly, the study found that the balancing allowance does not have a significant effect on the ROA. Unlike other tax incentives, a balancing allowance typically granted when an asset is disposed of for less than its tax written-down value may be more relevant to capital-intensive manufacturing sectors than to consumer goods firms. The insignificant result may indicate that consumer goods companies either do not fully use or prioritize this allowance, potentially due to low awareness or minimal impact on overall tax liabilities. This aligns with Ondabu, Muturi, and Kisaka (2016), who observed that not all tax incentives are equally effective across sectors. In summary, while tax relief, capital allowance, and investment allowance significantly enhance firm performance, the effectiveness of balancing allowance is limited within the consumer goods sector. These results underscore the importance of designing targeted tax policies that align with specific industries' operational realities and investment behaviors.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the effect of tax incentives on the performance of consumer goods companies in Nigeria, with a focus on how tax relief, capital allowance, investment allowance, and balancing allowance influence return on assets (ROA) as a measure of performance. The analysis revealed that tax relief has a significant

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positive effect on ROA, indicating that reducing the tax burden enhances firms' financial capacity. This allows companies to allocate more resources toward core operations, expansion, and innovation, ultimately improving profitability. Similarly, CA showed a significant positive impact on ROA, suggesting that enabling firms to deduct capital expenditures from taxable income encourages investment in physical and technological infrastructure and directly contributes to improved operational performance and cost efficiency. Investment allowance also had a significant positive effect on ROA, highlighting the importance of incentivizing investment through tax deductions, which can facilitate the acquisition of income-generating assets and support long-term strategic growth in the consumer goods sector. In contrast, the balancing allowance did not exhibit a significant effect on ROA. This may reflect its limited applicability or infrequent use within the consumer goods industry or inefficiencies in its implementation relative to more impactful tax measures.

Overall, the findings affirm that targeted tax incentives can significantly enhance the performance of Nigerian consumer goods companies when effectively designed and administered. Such incentives stimulate capital formation, promote investment, reduce operational costs, and strengthen profitability and sustainability. From a policy perspective, the study underscores the need for government and tax authorities to prioritize and optimize effective tax incentives, particularly those that directly influence firm investment and operational capacity. Encouraging the use of capital and investment allowances while reassessing the relevance and execution of less effective incentives, such as balancing allowance, can enhance the overall tax system's efficacy. In conclusion, tax incentives remain a critical economic tool for boosting Nigeria's consumer goods sector's performance. However, their impact varies across different types of incentives, highlighting the importance of strategic policy design, periodic assessment, and sector-specific needs alignment.

The study recommends the following:

1. **Enhancing Tax Relief Programs:** Since tax relief has a significant positive effect on performance, the government should streamline and expand tax relief programs targeted at the consumer goods sector through the FIRS. This includes simplifying eligibility requirements and automating processes to ensure timely and consistent relief application.
2. **Maximizing Capital Allowance Benefits:** Given the significant impact of capital allowance on return on assets, regulatory authorities and professional bodies should organize workshops and issue clear guidelines to help consumer goods companies fully understand and maximize the benefits of capital allowances, particularly for capital-intensive projects such as digital infrastructure and business expansion.
3. **Strengthening Investment Allowances:** Since investment allowances significantly enhance performance, policymakers should revise existing policies to offer enhanced or additional incentives for companies investing in innovation, green technology, financial inclusion infrastructure, and cybersecurity systems. Such measures would improve firm performance while supporting broader national development objectives.
4. **Reviewing Balancing Allowance:** The government should conduct a comprehensive review of its relevance within the consumer goods sector because balancing allowance showed no significant impact on

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return on assets. This may involve updating the framework to better align with modern business operations or redirecting such incentives to areas with greater impact on firm performance.

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